

VENTILATION AND PERFUSION CONDITION OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND PULMONARY HYPERTENSION

**Rakhimova D.,
Alavi A.,
Nuriddinova S.**

State Institution "Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation" Tashkent, Uzbekistan, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

Abstract

To study interrelations psychological of factors regulations, and quality of life (QL) of the patients with remodeling right ventriculi of heart at the patients of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. complicated by cor pulmonale on a background of treatment standarttherapy, ozonotherapy (OT) and phototherapy (FT).

As a result of research have established, that OT and FT on a background of bazistherapy improve patogenesis the interconnected infringements that is psychological of factors regulations, parameters QL, diastolik function right ventriculi of heard and respiratory function ($p < 0,05$).

Keywords: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, respiratory status, quality of life, psychovegetative regulation factors, phototherapy.

Due to the fact that chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is complicated by the heart of the lungs, the consequences of disability, death increase year after year, the Prevention of diseases, when the diagnosis begins early, the terminal stages of the disease and the origin of the disability are obtained. The Prevention of the disease, the diagnosis of complications of the pulmonary heart in the early stages, the Coordination of modern methods of treatment, medical recovery, helps to cope with the problem posed [1,2].

In modern medicine, patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (sook), prevention of complications with pulmonary heart (PG) diagnosis and treatment – it is necessary to be early, effective, individual and multi-stage. Consequently, the development of an optimal plan for prevention and treatment of Oyu complication is an urgent problem, taking into account clinical-functional, pathogenetic and regional allochidism [3].

Prepared by the American Thoracic Society and the European Respiratory Society (ATS/ERS) Association, a report of clinical trials defines the role and stages of proof of SOOC rehabilitation [26].

Based on the developed programs, pulmonary rehabilitation-a complication of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, in order to prevent nausea, it is required to carry out 4 stage activities: I. Monitoring the disease; II. Reducing the impact of risk factors; III. Treatment of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in an advanced state; IV. Treatment of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in advanced condition [4].

According to the recommendations of "pulmonary rehabilitation", summarized with the European Respiratory Society (ERS) [27], when the effectiveness of Sook rehabilitation is analyzed, patients' capacity for physical disorders increases after some therapy treatments (proof phase A). Shortness of breath attacks are reduced (proof stage A). Quality of life improves (proof stage A). Anxiety and depression associated with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease are reduced (proof stage A). Psychosocial exposure is effective (proof Step S). The minimum duration of pulmonary

rehabilitation is 6 weeks; the effect increases when this period lasts longer (proof Stage V).

According to the analysis of European experts [28], the quality and duration of the life of patients is significantly improved when a lot of funds are spent on the adequate treatment of diseases and complications of the respiratory organs.

In the treatment of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in advanced condition, based on the materials of the Congress of the European Respiratory Society [25], the prolonged use of standardized base therapy prevents the development of cardiovascular complications.

Researchers [5] after treating patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with standard therapy based on ERS recommendations (proof stage A), reductions in quality of life parameters (positive variation from 3.3 ± 0.41 to 2.3 ± 0.35 points), number and duration of hospitalization (22.3 and 6.7 %) have been practically confirmed.

The impact of the training program on clinical-functional disorders and quality of life indicators in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease has been studied [18,23]. In this case, OFV1 was found to increase 1.8 times, with a quality of life tolerance to physical load of 79.2%, emotional state of 81.3%, and treatment satisfaction of 91.0% positive shifts.

Based on the [20,28] data in the literature, the low effectiveness of treatment of Oyu, especially during the peak period, forces the search for new approaches to solving this problem. One of the perspective directions in this scope is the use of medicamentous treatment methods. It would be appropriate to use β -blockers and calcium antagonists in the development of effective prevention and treatment methods in patients with a pulmonary heart, giving priority to clinical functional changes.

According to the data of the researchers [6] in the treatment of patients with complications of acute pulmonary arterial hypertension, a beta - adrenoblocator (Nebivolol) was used from drugs. With the help of one course of treatment with Nebivolol, those who ob-

served a decrease in the anterior wall of the right ventricle (axis) < 3.8 mm, the ventricle in the diastole of the heart < 22 mm, the ventricle in the systole of the heart < 15 mm. The decrease in weight that falls on the right ventricle of the heart is $E/a > 1.3$ and the decrease in pulmonary artery mean pressure (22 mm CM.who.) were identified in the calm state of patients.

According to the tests [7], patients with SOOC decompensator heart failure were found to have cardiac right-to-right fraction-FAF 16.7%, cardiac right ventricular isovoltic relaxation time-IVRT 13.6% declines when given cardioselective β -adrenoblocator-nebivolol. The noted changes are noted due to the decrease in endothelial dysfunction (nitric oxide stable metabolites - SMNO 6.7%), and methods of Correction with cardioselective β -adrenoblocators are recommended.

In the literature [8] they interpret the controversial issue of the use of beta-adrenoblocators in patients with subsequent pulmonary - cardiac complications. That is, in diseases of the respiratory organs, one of the problems of choosing hypotensive agents based on basis therapy is bronchoobstruction, an indication against the use of B-blockers. Even today, methods of achieving a high effect in the treatment of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with acute complications with drugs, including: beta - adrenoblocators, are actively being prescribed.

The relative analysis of the effect of nebivolol on cardiac right ventricular remodeling and diastole dysfunction in 54 patients with [9] saliva in the tests is a notable reference. Based on the result of practical application, the peripheral hemodynamics resistance index in patients (0.92 ± 0.05 sh.b. from 0.81 ± 0.04 sh.b. gacha), pulmonary ventilation-perfusion disorder, have been found to be properly correlated to blood saturation. However, it has been noted that the effect on Central hemodynamics and plans for long-term use as a base therapy have not been developed.

Researchers [10] found that patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and arterial hypertension were advised small doses when using cardioselective b-blockers: metoprolol, bisoprolol, betaxolol. In the dynamics of treatment, first of all, the level of clinical symptoms, ECG and bronchoobstruction are monitored. Scientific investigations have analyzed the superiority of high-cardioselective bisoprolol over atenolol, even in terms of its effect on bronchial permeability. B-blockers with very few bronchoconstrictor properties (atsebutolol, pindolol), actively acting on the internal sympathomimetic system, have been noted to have relatively low hypotensive effect. That is, in peripheral hemodynamics, it is observed that macrophagal reduces nitric oxide production (3.3 %) and neurogumoral management does not significantly affect indicators.

Significant successes have been achieved in subsequent years in the treatment of Oyu complication with calcium antagonists, which have been studied to improve the course and consequences of the disease. Since it has no negative effect on bronchial conduction, calcium antagonists are chosen as the first remedy for the treatment of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

when it is complicated by pulmonary arterial hypertension [12]. But not all the effect effects of these Guru remedies have been sufficiently studied. Dihydropyridine-based (nifedipine, felodipine, amlodipine, lasidipine I dr from calcium channel blockers in the treatment of general and pulmonary arterial hypertension.) and dihydropyridine baseless (verapamil, diltiazem) agents are used. At the same time, according to researchers, the use of calcium antagonists (verapamil I diltiazem) is limited when the heart rhythm changes (bradyarrhythmias) and conductance (atrioventricular and sinoatrial blockades) is impaired. In scientific data, the fact that calcium antagonists have no negative effect on mucosiliary clearance of the bronchi has an important acuity in the treatment of systemic complications in patients with sook [33].

In the Tests [13] it was established that patients with non-exacerbation of the disease but with varying degrees of hypoxemia and pulmonary artery hypertension had a decrease in the dynamics of treatment with calcium antagonists, the average pressure of the pulmonary artery (28.3 ± 0.7 mm.CM.ust. to 22.4 mm.CM.ust., i.e. 16.7 %) and resistance (13.3%). The mechanism of action of calcium antagonists in patients with saliva has been interpreted. That is, it positively affects the small and large circulatory system by reducing vasoconstriction and cardiac weight developed at the expense of hypoxia, and dystrophic and sclerotic changes in the myocardium by lowering the calling hypoxia.

According to researchers [14], calcium antagonists simultaneously attenuate bronchoconstriction and reduce mediator output. Calcium antagonists affect all stages in which bronchoobstruction develops. In particular, acetylcholine, histamine, leukotriene and prostaglandins reduce the calling bronchospasm, the mucous membrane of smooth muscles, fat cells, bronchi has a positive effect on secretory cells. Calcium antagonists occupy a worthy place in the treatment of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in adulthood, due to the fact that they do not adversely affect metabolic processes and coordinate the functioning of the kidneys.

Researchers [15] when patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease are given a course of calcium antagonists, metabolic alkalosis (22.0%) in the normal state of total arterial pressure and uncompensated respiratory failure, $RSO_2 < 35$ mm.rt.st.those who recorded positive shifts in quantity. Calcium antagonists have been shown in clinical trials to have lost pulmonary regional vasoconstriction and not affected the overall ratio of pulmonary ventilation - perfusion.

Researchers [34] report that when acute testing with calcium antagonists reduces the average pressure of the pulmonary artery in the early stages of pulmonary artery hypertension, it is noted that pulmonary artery hypertension does not affect in the later stages (increased resistance, increased pulmonary artery hypertension in exchange for morphological changes).

The authors [16] examined the condition of the right ventricle of the heart of the population living in high mountain (2400-3100 m) conditions using invasive and noninvasive functional methods, assessing

cardiac axial diastole dysfunction and cardiac axial diastole Reserve in the early stages. When using calcium antagonists for 12 weeks in the treatment of advanced acute complications due to hypoxia, in a patient with 30 sooks, the resistance of the pulmonary vessels decreased by 23.4±2.0%, the anterior wall of the right ventricle of the heart is 2.3±0.1 cm. from 2.0±0.1 CM. a decrease of up to ($p=0.042$) has been observed. According to the conclusions, when individual therapy is given to an individual patient over a long period of time, a decrease in pulmonary arterial hypertension (from 41.7 mm.CM.ust., up to 31.8 mm.CM.UST., $p<0.05$) has been analyzed. The results of such research are not many and in different interpretations, since the authors used different drugs, dosages, treatment times.

Fisnman A.P. [35] according to their examinations, vasodilator therapy is performed, and patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease complicated by pulmonary artery hypertension are given a dose of 0.005 g of verapamil intravenous injection with increased cardiac right ventricular firing charge and decreased overall arterial pressure and resistance. It has been hypothesized that pulmonary artery resistance decreased in only 65% of patients with 30% of pulmonary artery mean pressure in patients. In his opinion, calcium antagonists are effective in relation to recurrent pulmonary artery hypertension, the opposite effect is observed when organic changes are in the vascular system.

Cremona G., Higenbottam T. et al. [36] an improvement in External respiratory activity (OFV, -36.3±2.4% to 43.3±3.3 %) ($r<0.05$) and Central hemodynamics (E/A 0.95 to 1.3) was noted by the authors when amlodipine was administered for 4 Weeks, 5-10 mg per day in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Calcium antagonists do not have a negative effect on the sexual activity of patients, it has been noted that dihydropyridines can even improve.

In " Endothelin-receptor antagonists in pulmonary hypertension (EAPH) " examinations, they recommend long-term treatment by lowering pulmonary artery mean pressure (spinal < 22.1 mm.CM.ust.) when using calcium antagonists in acute sinamas, improving peripheral hemodynamics maximum systolic rate (Vmax 6.2 %) and increasing blood oxygen saturation (SaO₂ 81.3±2.4%).

In some sources [17], calcium antagonists have long been used, and negative effects on the suspension, eliminating all the positive effect they have shown. At this time, it is important to remember that if the adverse effects are corrected by a differentiated approach, a significant calculation of general hypotonia and strong tachycardia, and the dose is corrected, such unpleasant effects as peripheral redness, feeling of hot arrival, ankle tumors scare the treating doctors.

The seeker [18] studied the effect of calcium antagonists on the quality of life of patients with sook with a tolerance of physical loads of 1.3 times (326.6±29.1 to 210.0±20.7 m.up to; $R<0.02$) increase, performance, and psychological status indicators have been found to have positive shifts of -16.8 Δ% in scores. Patients have reports of depression, decreased

fear, and improved sexual functioning. Significant successes have been achieved in subsequent years in the treatment of Oyu with calcium antagonists, which have been studied to improve the development and consequences of the disease. In scientific research, calcium antagonists in sook patients with pulmonary arterial hypertension, negative changes in hypotonia (systolic arterial pressure decreases from 145 mm.CM.ust. to 90 mm.CM.UST.) and heart rhythms (LF/YF 2.3 %) are cited.

It is known that prostaglandins from other guruh drugs used in patients with Oyu-complicated sook provide vascular tone in the norm and pathology, reduce platelet aggregation. According to opinions, in patients with pulmonary arterial hypertension, prostaglandins are used in cases where calcium antagonists are ineffective or impossible [20]. But, not all the effects of these Guru remedies on patients with sook have been sufficiently studied.

In scientific research on the treatment of patients with pulmonary-heart complications using angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (Aphis), the use of general and pulmonary artery hypertension was carried out. In their research, [21] methods of obtaining a large positive effect were found when treating patients together with Apfi and fenspiride against colds (sook Grade II, during the period of complications with compensated Oyu), together with Apfi and fluticazone against colds (sook Grade III-IV, during the period of complications with uncompensated Oyu).

Joint statements by European pulmonologists and the American Thoracic communities [26] give instructions for long-term use of oxygenotherapy in patients with sook. Based on the recommendations, the practice noted an improvement in patient quality of life (9.8%), an increase in capacity (2.3%), a decrease in mortality as a result of an extension of the remission period (1.2%).

Sources studied the use of efferent therapy in medicine, [22] interpreting that the restoration of the form of erythrocytes after ozonotherapy is determined by an increase in its surface and an improvement in their functional properties. Another effect of ozone on the rheological properties of blood is the activation of the enzyme no synthetase in endothelial cells, caused by the action of ozone on endothelial cells of the vascular wall. In diseases of the internal organs, in the dynamics of treatment with ozone oxygen compounds, the oxygen saturation of the blood (SaO₂ 8.2 %) increases, analyzing the decrease in the number of heart contractions from 1 minute: 81.6±0.3 to 73.1±0.4. This is due to the properties of ozone that transport oxygen and release it in tissues.

Experiments have shown that ozone can react with amino acids, the descendants of biologically active substances (dopamine, norepinephrine, adrenaline) in vitro. As a result, it can be assumed that the rapid delivery of fatty acids, which play a key role in the muscle activity of the heart, decreases the breakdown of glucose as energy [23]. Vasodilation factor-pulmonary selective vasodilator, high diffusion-nitric oxide ingestion reduces pulmonary arterial hypertension. In this case, nitric oxide is rapidly added with hemoglobin,

does not enter into large circulation and does not call for general hypotonia, that is, it is active only in the small circulatory system [24]. To determine the effectiveness of vasodilation therapy, patients are listed as the "gold standard" for conducting a prognostic, acute test with nitric oxide.

In addition, there are data on the use of nitrous oxide with positive effects for 2 years (10 treatments per 1 course, every 3 months). With long application of nitric oxide, the vessels caused by hypoxia corrects the structure and dystrophy of the endothelial system and vasodilation is achieved. Also, pulmonary artery pressure is corrected, inducing regression of morphological changes such as cardiac right ventricular remodeling [25].

Conclusions:

Prevention of complications with the pulmonary heart (Oyu) in patients with sook diagnosis and treatment – it is necessary to be early, effective, individual and multi-stage.

During the period of pulmonary heart diagnosis, it will be appropriate for patients to use effective prevention and treatment methods: long-term use of base therapy, the use of β -blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (Aphis), prostaglandins and calcium antagonists.

Long-term use of oxygenotherapy and ozonotherapy in patients with sook improves the oxygen saturation of the blood and the rheological properties of the blood.

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